

Thorium(IV) Fluorosulphate

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$\text{Th}(\text{SO}_3\text{F})_4$, [A], has been prepared by the action of HSO_3F on $\text{Th}(\text{O}_2\text{CCH}_3)_4$. The i.r. spectrum indicates bidentate nature of SO_3F groups. It forms adducts with pyridine (Py), quinoline (Q), dimethylsulphoxide (DMSO), triphenylphosphineoxide (TPPO) and bipyridyl (Bipy) of the compositions, A. 2Py, A. 2Q, A. 2DMSO, A. 2TPPO and A. Bipy respectively. SO_3F groups in these complexes are also bidentate as shown by their i.r. spectra. $\text{Th}(\text{SO}_3\text{F})_4$ decomposes thermally in a single step with evolution of SO_2F_2 and formation of $\text{Th}(\text{SO}_4)_2$.

A variety of uranium fluorosulphates viz; $\text{U}(\text{SO}_3\text{F})_4$, $\text{UF}_2(\text{SO}_3\text{F})_3$, $\text{UF}(\text{SO}_3\text{F})_4$, $\text{UF}_3(\text{SO}_3\text{F})_2$ and $\text{UO}_2(\text{SO}_3\text{F})_2(1-4)$ are the only actinide fluorosulphates reported so far. We report in this communication the preparation and characterization of thorium(IV) fluorosulphate and its coordination complexes with some nitrogen and oxygen donors.

Experimental

Fluorosulphuric acid was purified by double distillation⁶. Anhydrous thorium acetate was prepared by refluxing thorium nitrate hexahydrate with a mixture of acetic acid and acetic anhydride (40:60% by vol). Ligands and solvents were purified and distilled before use. SO_2Cl_2 (E. Merck) was used as such.

Preparation of $\text{Th}(\text{SO}_3\text{F})_4$ and its Complexes: $\text{Th}(\text{SO}_3\text{F})_4$ was prepared by adding an excess (6-8 fold) of HSO_3F to a known weight of $\text{Th}(\text{O}_2\text{CCH}_3)_4$. The contents were refluxed for 2 hr. The white solid formed was filtered in the atmosphere of dry N_2 gas, repeatedly washed with fluorosulphuric acid followed by SO_2Cl_2 and finally dried *in vacuo*.

The coordination complexes, A.2Py, A.2Q, A. 2DMSO, A.2TPPO and A. Bipy were prepared by adding the ligand in a stoichiometric amount to the suspension of A in solvent and stirring the contents at room temperature for about 20 hr. Carbon tetrachloride was used as the solvent for pyridine and quinoline complexes, while benzene was the solvent for other complexes. The products were filtered under nitrogen, washed with the respective solvent and dried *in vacuo*.

Instrumentation and Analytical Methods: Infrared spectra of the compounds were recorded as nujol or hexachlorobutadiene mulls or as thin solid films in silver chloride, cesium iodide or polythene plates

on Perkin-Elmer-621 spectrophotometer. Thermal analysis was carried out by means of a Stanton Thermobalance Model TR-I at a heating rate of 4°/minute.

Thorium was determined as $\text{ThO}_2(6)$. Sulphur and fluorine were determined by hydrolysing a known weight of the compound with 10% sodium hydroxide solution, sulphur as $\text{BaSO}_4(6)$ and fluorine volumetrically by titrating against standard thorium nitrate solution using Alizarin red-S as an indicator. C, H and N were determined micro-analytically by microanalyst of the department. The analytical results are shown in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

$\text{Th}(\text{O}_2\text{CCH}_3)_4$ reacts with HSO_3F exothermally and refluxing yields the white solid, $\text{Th}(\text{SO}_3\text{F})_4$. It is a hygroscopic solid, insoluble in usual organic solvents as well as fluorosulphuric acid. The thermogram of $\text{Th}(\text{SO}_3\text{F})_4$ was recorded upto 600°. It is stable upto 160°, above this temperature it decomposes endothermally in a single step. The observed loss in weight 32.18% (calc. 32.48%) corresponds to the evolution of two moles of SO_2F_2 . The final weight of the residue and its elemental analysis corresponds to $\text{Th}(\text{SO}_4)_2$. The evolution of SO_2F_2 during the decomposition of $\text{Th}(\text{SO}_3\text{F})_4$ was confirmed from the infrared spectrum of the gaseous products obtained by heating it in a separate experiment.

Infrared spectrum of $\text{Th}(\text{SO}_3\text{F})_4$ (Table 2) shows the presence of nine fundamental vibrational modes expected for a fluorosulphate group having C_2 symmetry. The $\nu\text{S}-\text{O}$ modes appearing at 1360, 1170 and 1075 cm^{-1} indicate the bidentate nature of fluorosulphate groups⁷⁻⁹. The $\nu\text{S}-\text{F}$ appears at 840 cm^{-1} only. From these observations, eight coordination around thorium is anticipated and the following structure for $\text{Th}(\text{SO}_3\text{F})_4$ may be

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TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA

Sl. No.	Compound	Found(%)						Calculated(%)					
		Th	S	F	C	H	N	Th	S	F	C	H	N
1.	A.	36.72	20.64	12.71	—	—	—	36.94	20.38	12.10	—	—	—
2.	A. 2Py	29.04	16.75	9.82	15.10	1.81	3.46	29.51	16.28	9.67	15.27	1.27	3.56
3.	A. 2Q	26.02	14.56	9.65	24.16	1.52	3.02	26.18	14.44	8.57	24.38	1.58	3.16
4.	A. 2DMSO	29.48	25.06	9.62	6.10	1.58	—	29.59	24.48	9.69	6.12	1.53	—
5.	A. 2TPPO	19.23	11.12	6.98	35.13	2.68	—	19.59	10.81	6.42	36.48	2.53	—
6.	A. Bipy	29.62	16.96	9.54	15.50	1.10	3.48	29.59	16.32	9.69	15.30	1.02	3.57

proposed (Fig. 1). The X-ray structure can, however, throw more light, provided suitable crystals for these insoluble fluorosulphate can be obtained.

Fig. 1

The infrared spectra of the complexes (Table 2) reveal that fluorosulphate groups are again behaving as bidentate ligands, as no significant change is observed from the parent fluorosulphate vibrations. One of the three ν S—O modes which in

$\text{Th}(\text{SO}_3\text{F})_4$ appears at 1360 cm^{-1} shifts to *ca.* 1300 cm^{-1} in the complexes. The important ligand vibrations listed in the table show a significant shift in the diagnostic stretching vibrations of various bases¹⁰⁻¹⁵, which implies, that these ligands are coordinated to thorium in these complexes. These observations lead to the conclusion that thorium is ten coordinated in these complexes. Such a coordination number for thorium has been observed in thorium(IV) nitrate complexes with similar ligands¹⁶.

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 TABLE 2—INFRARED SPECTRAL DATA (cm^{-1})

A	A. 2Py	A. 2Q	A. 2DMSO	A. 2TPPO	A. Bipy	Assignment
	1610	1650			1630	
	1605	1605			1590	Ligand
	1565	1565			1540	vibrations
	1495	1495	1420	1445	1450	
1360	1300	1310	1315	1300	1300	$\nu_4(\text{E})$
1170	1150	1155	1160	1160	1140	
—	—	—	—	1115	—	ligand
1075	1030	1075	1050	1065	1075	$\nu_1(\text{A}_1)$
—	—	—	985	—	1015	ligand
840	855	860	830	845	840	$\nu_3(\text{A}_1)$
—	—	—	705	—	770	
—	—	—	—	—	740	ligand
610	—	670	625	665	660	$\nu_5(\text{E})$
575	575	590	565	—	570	
545	555	550	550	545	535	$\nu_2(\text{A}_1)$
450	460	470	465	455	470	
380	375	390	405	380	375	$\nu_6(\text{E})$